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Demographic Transition and Social Sector Challenges in India :
Understanding Demographic Dynamics

Agricultural Growth, Rural Poverty, and Sustainable Development

India's External Sector Reforms and Challenges

Exploring Tourism Opportunities and Overcoming Challenges in Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand

Climate Change and Environmental Degradation: A Global Challenge

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Examining Socio-Economic Disparities in Healthcare Access: A Case Study of Uttar Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

We will have been a nation for 100 years by 2047. According to GDP, India currently is the fifth-largest economy in the world. By 2027, we estimate India's GDP to be worth \$5 trillion. In spite of its 75 years of independence, numerous accomplishments, and significant economic expansion in recent times, India continues to lag behind and struggle to match the world's top economies in the healthcare sector. It is ranked 66 in global health security index 2021.

Numerous inefficiencies exist in India's public health system, including disparities in access to healthcare between urban and rural areas, inadequate infrastructure in certain areas, a scarcity of medical professionals, insufficient funding, and challenges in providing healthcare to a sizable and diverse population. Even if there are more and more millionaires and billionaires in the country rising, the lowest quintile still lacks access to essential healthcare amenities.

The developed nations of the world like the USA, Italy etc. have a healthy population not because of its wealth, but rather because of its well-being and a strong public healthcare system.

The Indian healthcare system is divided into three tiers: primary, secondary, and tertiary. Primary healthcare is deemed to be the most crucial factor in ensuring healthcare facilities at the initial level. However, the research indicates that at this level, there exist a variety of disparities. To ensure that everyone has an equal access to primary healthcare, which would support the services being provided at the secondary and tertiary level and ultimately ensure a robust healthcare system at the state level, the government may play a crucial role. The study primarily focuses on the preparedness of Uttar Pradesh's healthcare system and identifies significant obstacles to the provision of high-quality services.

Keywords: Healthcare, Inequalities, Economic growth, Innovation, Primary healthcare.

Introduction

India's health sector has always presented major challenges to policy makers by demanding increased budgetary expenditure every year in proportion to the desired outcomes for a healthy

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nation. Experts have accepted the fact that there is a strong relationship between economic growth and better health and it is a two-way relationship. A population with major health problems can never be a part of the growth process of the nation. On the other hand, a nation surrounded by health problems can adversely affect the country's development goals. The Millennium Development Goals and later the Sustainable Development Goals included this and the integrated health goals in their agenda. Have done. Having signed the Sustainable Development Goals, India now has the responsibility to formulate and implement its policies to achieve those goals. There is a need to set health priorities. With our development policies it is much more important and needed to work in this area. Our policy makers understood this and initiated several health related programs in the past, which have been extremely successful. Our vaccination programmes, especially the globally acclaimed pulse polio, have reduced infant and maternal mortality rates and we have almost won the battle against the once deadly smallpox. Financing healthcare is a key component of providing health care in the world. Financing healthcare is a key component of providing healthcare. In India, the government largely operates its own large public healthcare system. Yet a large portion of population must seek medical care outside the system. Healthcare has become one of the most expensive services for any person from the middle and lower classes. Therefore, the government needs to put more efforts to improve primary health care. The challenges of healthcare for tribals, women, adolescents and youth from north eastern regions are different from those of the general population. Health services in tribal areas require a different approach, which can be region specific and sensitive to the tribals, in which participation and empowerment of the local population can be fully ensured and the lack of knowledge and behavior change can be addressed. To bridge the gap, health literacy and communication can be made a major and strategic medium. Similarly, the different health needs of men and women are important for the welfare of the nation. To ensure the justice for men and women in the country, it is necessary to eliminate malnutrition among women, especially pregnant women and children. When a large section of the population remains undernourished, the economic development of the country is definitely affected. The need of the hour is to intensify primary health services and the skilled medical professionals need to add to the workforce. Primary level healthcare needs to be improved. India's primary healthcare system plays a crucial role in addressing the diverse health challenges across the country, aiming to make healthcare accessible and affordable for all citizens. However, challenges such as uneven distribution of resources and infrastructure gaps persist in some regions. A nation with healthy people will be able to contribute to and achieve its development goals and make India stronger and more vibrant.

About Uttar Pradesh:-

Uttar Pradesh is the most populous state of India with approx 24.14 crore population. As per NITI AAYOG state health index Uttar Pradesh secured last position in the category of larger states. There are a variety of disparities found in the health care system of Uttar Pradesh. The western part of Uttar Pradesh is healthier and wealthier than the Central part, Bundelkhand region and Eastern UP. The health amenities in UP are in a better position but not accessible and affordable. Eastern Uttar Pradesh is suffering from many problems in which disparities in health care services are one of the biggest challenges in this region. During monsoon the eastern part of Uttar Pradesh is inundated and makes it tough for the population to access the existing services. Access to healthcare services

is the major problem among so many problems of the healthcare system. Socio-economic inequalities seep into the health sector and disproportionately affect health outcomes of marginalized communities. The western part of Uttar Pradesh is socioeconomically stronger than the Eastern part of the state and Bundelkhand is also in a better position than the Eastern part of the state .The districts of Eastern Uttar Pradesh are suffering with low health outcomes and poor health development.

The overall performance of Eastern Uttar Pradesh in terms of health attainment is pitiable. ‘INDIA INEQUALITY REPORT 2021 -India’s unequal healthcare story’ says that, “the general category is better off than SCs and STs, Hindus are better off than Muslims, the rich are better off than poor,men are better off than women and the urban population is better off than rural population”when it comes to healthcare access and on health indicators.. Social and economic inequalities are the major barriers which are affecting access to health services and are one of the major factors responsible for overall economic development of the state.

Table 1: UP in comparison to India

Indicators	Uttar Pradesh	India
infant mortality rate(per live births)	50.4	35.2
Under five mortality rate(per 1000 live births)	59.8	41.9
All children aged 6-23 months who are fed a healthy diet (%)	6.1	11.3
Children under 5 years who are stunted (height-for age)	39.7	35.5
Mothers who consume iron folic acid for at least 100 days during their pregnancies (%)	22.3	44.1

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS 5)

Findings:- The National Family Health Survey (NFHS) 5 data for Uttar Pradesh and a few other states was released by the government on November 24, 2021. The data shows the situation of people’s health in the state.The percentage of children under five years who are severely wasted has increased in UP from 6% in 2015-16 to 7.3% in 2020-21. The percentage of children aged 6-59 months who are anemic has also increased from 63% to 66% over the same period.Although the indicators on stunted and wasted children show marginal improvements, a recent response from the Women & Child Development Ministry to an RTI query from *The Hindu* notes that UP is home to nearly 1.86 lakh malnourished children.Data for UP also shows an increase in the percentage of anemic women aged 15- 19 years. The prevalence of obesity has also increased in 2020-21 as compared to 2015-16 with the proportion of obese people (in all categories - men, women and children) increasing substantially in UP.In comparison to India’s average, UP remains a laggard state in many of the important health indicators. Table 1 below shows some of these indicators in which UP has fared poorly than the national average.Although there is a decline in IMR in UP as compared to NFHS 4 data, but looking at the India average, UP severely underperforms. It is a matter of serious concern that in UP, nearly 50 children die per 1000 live births. For India, on an

average, this figure is 35. The latest data shows that not only has India missed the target, but UP fares much poorly. Similarly, U5MR is much higher in UP as compared to India. In UP, nearly 60 children per 1000 live births die below five years of age; for India this figure is about 42. The NHP targets reducing U5MR to 23 by 2025, but clearly the current levels are dissatisfactory. The indicators of malnutrition are alarming in the northern state as well. There are about two stunted children in every five children (under five years of age) in UP (40%). The share of wasted children (under five years of age) in UP stands at 17%. A study by Jean Dreze and Vipul Paikra shows that in states such as UP, where the health services are already in a poor condition in normal times, the period of lockdowns during 2020 witnessed a collapse of these services. They studied the Health Management Information System data and compared the April-May 2020 average as a ratio of the January-February 2020 average, and also the April-May 2020 average as a ratio of the April-May 2019 average. In UP, there has been a deterioration in some key indicators such as child wasting and anemia over the years. The improvement in others has been rather slow over the past five years (between NFHS 4 and 5). The data shows that Uttar Pradesh is not performing well in healthcare due to several inequalities found in the region. Women and children are the most affected and primary healthcare could be an approach to reduce the inequality and provide necessary healthcare to all.

Way forward:-

There is a talk everywhere about the demographic dividend of India but it is also a matter of concern that either this young population could take the country to the top or it could be a burden. One of the most important factors to make young population productive is providing them with best health facilities. As the paper is concerned, there are disparities found in the access to healthcare services. So various steps need to be taken in this direction. Increase funding for healthcare infrastructure, ensuring a well equipped and accessible network of primary health centers, hospitals and clinics, strengthen training programs, skilled healthcare professionals, addressing the shortage of skilled personnel, especially in rural areas. Embracing digital health solutions to enhance healthcare delivery, telemedicine, electronic health records and data analytics for better resource allocation, encouraging collaborations between the government and private sector to improve efficiency, resource utilization, and expand healthcare access. A comprehensive and collaborative effort involving government, healthcare professionals, communities, and the private sector can contribute to significant improvements in India's healthcare system.

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